

From
biowaste
to soil
regeneration

Bin2Bean

Why do we need to act?

30%

of Municipal waste
is biowaste

80%

of the biowaste is
landfilled or
incinerated

These are
precious
resources..

..that can be
turned into very
much needed soil
improvers

65%

of European soils
are unhealthy

17%

of biowaste is
recycled and just a
fraction used to
improve soils

The approach of the Bin2Bean project: defining the best solutions for your city

In practice..

- 1.** Local stakeholders will identify the best replicable solutions in terms of biowaste collection and soil improvers production
- 2.** Partners will test methods to demonstrate the safety of soil improvers, and indicators for soil quality
- 3.** Issue of guidelines for policymakers to improve biowaste collection and favor the adoption of soil improvers

Take part in Bin2Bean

Supporting
European Cities by
promoting effective
circular solutions

3 Living labs:

AMSTERDAM (NL)

EGALEO (EL)

HAMBURG (DE)

Project partners

Consorzio
Italbiotec

STADTREINIGUNG.HAMBURG

SHAPING THE
CIRCULAR ECONOMY

A WARRANT HUB COMPANY

RUOKAVIRASTO
Livsmedelverket • Finnish Food Authority

NACHHALTIGKEITSBERATUNG
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